

Forensic accounting and fraud

A review of literature and policy implications

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Abstract:

Some evidence about fraud, forensic accounting, and the qualifications and training of forensic investigators are presented in this paper. Additionally, a brief discussion of the differences in opinion between regulators and academics about the identification of fraud is given. I answer the query of regulators as to why forensic accounting academic research is not very important in setting policy. Additionally, I offer some a wide range of issues and point up some crucial avenues for forensic accounting research in the future. This essay is meant to encourage discussions and additional study on the concerns raised.

Key words: Fraud, forensic accounting, fraud triangle, forensic education.

Introduction

The literature on fraud and forensic accounting is reviewed in this paper. In order to support any investigation process or activity, forensic accounting is defined for the purposes of this review as the process of comprehending, recognising, detecting, and notifying stakeholders about fraud patterns and schemes. Accounting rules give management latitude in how they disclose financial information. Nonetheless, there are worries that executive discretion may be exploited and used both to commit and cover up dishonest business practises. Thus, forensic accounting is required. However, to ensure the quality of any forensic work, the fraud expert or investigator must be informed about the various ways that fraud is committed, how it appears, how it is concealed, and how to identify it. This review, which is driven by this issue, looks at earlier forensic accounting research and makes recommendations for both policy and scholarly study.

Scholars in the field of forensic accounting stress the need of forensic accounting education. On the other hand, nothing is known concerning inadvertent repercussions of forensic accounting instruction. There isn't much written on this topic. As a result, this review addresses this issue as a gap in the most recent research. This study also raises an interesting question regarding the appropriateness of giving every fraud case the same level of investigative priority. In the same way that doctors do not allocate the same level of resources to every type of illness because they do not view every condition as potentially fatal. Similarly, it is simple to comprehend why authorities respond differently to multiple reported fraud situations by applying this example. In conclusion, this review adds to the body of knowledge on forensic accounting.

The format of this review is as follows. Forensic accounting and fraud are covered in Sections 2 and 3. The literature on the training and qualifications of forensic investigators is reviewed in Section 4. A few concerns of policy and practise are covered in Section 5. Section 6 is the end.

Define Fraud

"The purposeful attempt by corporations to prepare and disseminate materially misstated financial statements in order to deceive or mislead users of published financial statements, especially investors and creditors, is known as financial statement fraud." Rezaee (2005), p. 279. There is a wealth of information available on fraud (see, for example, Apostolou et al., 2000; Rezaee, 2005; Ozkul and Pamukcu, 2012, etc.). Together, the research demonstrates a degree of agreement that fraud may entail: (1) the deliberate misapplication and misinterpretation of accounting standards, principles, policies, and methods used to measure, recognise, and report economic events and business transactions; (2) intentional misstatements, omissions, or misrepresentations of events, transactions, accounts, or other significant information from which financial statements are prepared; (3) the manipulation or alteration of material financial records, supporting documents, or business transactions; (4) purposeful disclosures and omissions from the presentation (5) the application of aggressive accounting techniques, such as fraudulent earnings management schemes; and (6) the manipulation of accounting procedures in accordance with rule- or principle-based accounting standards, which permits businesses to conceal the real financial performance of their operations.

Fraud schemes differ in terms of their breadth, setting, and the individuals involved's position within the company. Because of incentives connected to the industry, some forms of fraud are exclusive to certain industries (Calavita et al., 1997, for example). For instance, the banking and financial services sectors frequently experience investment and securities fraud. Top and middle management levels are the focus of other fraud categories (e.g., Crumbley, 2003; Zahra et al, 2005; etc.). Additional forms of fraud perpetrated by staff members include fabricating expenses and getting paid for them, establishing "ghost employees" and getting paid for them, establishing "ghost suppliers" and getting paid for them, reaping the rewards of exaggerated personal spending, etc. Pamukcu and Ozkul (2012). Accounting fraud frequently takes the form of manipulating accounting data used to produce financial reports, such as overvaluing inventories and improperly capitalising capital expenses (Harris & Brown, 2000; Messmer, 2004), managing earnings (Healy and Wahlen, 1999), and smoothing income (Ahmed et al., 1999; Curcio and Hasan, 2013; Ozili, 2015, etc.).

Fraud Motivations

The Fraud Triangle

→ Compensation Incentives/Pressure

There are several reasons to commit fraud, including financial, social, and personal requirements as well as the requirement to fulfil criteria for compensation. There is proof that managers are more likely to commit fraud when incentive schemes are in place. For instance, Johnson et al. (2003) discovered a substantial correlation between organisations with a history of fraud and incentives and pressures related to compensation. Denis et al. (2005) documented similar evidence.

There is a correlation between the employment of incentive schemes and fraud risk, according to Hernandez and Groot (2007). They specifically looked at auditors' perceptions of incentives that raise the risk of fraud.

They determined that the employment of incentive schemes, dishonest communications, and unethical attitudes by top management were significant predictors of fraud risk or likelihood. According to Efendi et al. (2007), when a CEO has a significant number of stock options and the company is subject to debt covenants, there is a higher chance that financial statements would be misrepresented. Additional proof of incentive-related fraud can be found in Burns and Kedia (2006) and Lie (2005). Erickson et al. (2000), on the other hand, looked into the connection between financial statement

fraud and equity incentives. They looked at companies who were accused of fraud between 1996 and 2003 and discovered no connection between accounting fraud and stock incentives.

These contradictory findings seem to indicate that managers are not always motivated to commit fraud by compensation schemes. Future studies are therefore required to pinpoint the precise incentives that encourage managers to commit fraud as well as the incentives that discourage them from doing so.

→ **Opportunities**

When there is a motive to perpetrate fraud, the perpetrator will look for a "opportunity" to carry out the deception. Ineffective monitoring and control systems (Beasley, 1996; Albrecht and Albrecht, 2003; etc.) are generally associated with a higher likelihood of fraud (Beasley, 1996; Dechow et al., 1996; McMullen and Raganandan, 1996; Farber, 2005), as are fewer audit committee meetings and a lower proportion of financial experts on the audit committee (Abbott et al., 2004; Farber, 2005; etc.). According to Beasley (1996), compared to non-fraud firms, the percentage of independent members on the board of directors is lower for companies that participate in fraud practises. These research' findings imply that opportunities for fraud are created by insufficient monitoring.

→ **Rationalizations**

The third element of the fraud triangle is rationalisation. When someone with a motive to perpetrate fraud finds a chance to do so, they will look for justifications for their behaviour. Claims such as "I borrowed the money," "I would pay back," "nobody has suffered as a result of this," "I didn't know it was a crime," and so on are examples of justifications (see Ozkul and Pamukcu, 2012; 24).

There is general agreement in the literature about the existence of a relationship between opportunities, rationalisation, and incentives.

However, there is disagreement over the incidence order or sequence for each element of the fraud triangle. Future studies should therefore aim to create a logical and systematic hierarchy between the fraud triangle's elements—incentives, opportunities, rationalisation, and capabilities—while also allowing for interdependence between them.

→ **Fraud Polygon**

The fraud triangle has been attempted to be expanded in a number of research. The fraud triangle was enlarged by Wolfe and Hermanson (2004), who gave it a fourth dimension they called the "fraud diamond." Ability is the fourth dimension. Wolfe and Hermanson (2004) claim that "capability" takes into account the fact that some persons will not conduct fraud, even in the case when all three of the original elements are highly present. The fraudster needs to be able to carry out the fraudulent conduct with some degree of assurance that it won't be noticed.

Additionally, Rezaee (2005) offers an alternative to the fraud triangle in an effort to pinpoint possible fraud sources. Rezaee (2005) looked into variables that could make someone more likely to commit fraud. He called this notion CRIME, where "C" stood for cooking the books, "R" for recipes, "I" for incentives, "M" for monitoring—or not—and "E" for end results. Based on his CRIME research, Rezaee (2005) came to the conclusion that financial statement fraud poses a severe risk to investors' trust in financial data. In a more recent work, Kranacher et al. (2010) developed their "MICE" theory to explain why people commit fraud. Kranacher et al. (2010) state that Fraud is motivated by MICE, or money, ideology, coercion, and ego/entitlement. They employed a co-joined triangle that resembled the fraud diamond in their analysis, but they kept the fraud triangle's structure intact.

According to earlier study, there's a chance that in the near future, sophisticated fraud instances will emerge and future academic research will deepen our understanding of fraud, hence enlarging the fraud triangle and fraud diamond. The fraud polygon is this extra dimension. The fraud polygon's concept is to create a logical and systematic order among recently developed fraud motivations while also allowing for dependency between them all.

Forensic Accounting Perspectives

According to Bolgna and Linquist (1995), forensic accounting is the process of applying investigative techniques and financial knowledge to unresolved problems while operating within the bounds of the standards of evidence. According to Arokiasamy and Cristal-Lee (2009) and Ozkul and Pamukc (2012), forensic accounting is the application of accounting and auditing, financial, and investigative abilities to unresolved issues within the framework of the rules of evidence. According to this definition, forensic accounting's main goal is to locate and examine fraudulent transactions in order to determine the true motivation of the culprit. This kind of review could be conducted by document reviews, interviews, electronic document inspections, etc.

According to Arokiasamy and Cristal-Lee (2009) and Dhar and Sarkar (2010), forensic accounting is the application of auditing methodologies, techniques, or procedures to address legal concerns from the viewpoint of an auditor. This involves integrating accounting, auditing, and investigation abilities. Forensic accounting, from the viewpoint of a lawyer or litigator, is obtaining, analysing, summarising, and presenting complicated financial matters in a precise, concise, and factual manner, frequently in a court of law as an expert (Howard and Sheetz, 2006; Stanbury and Paley-Menzies, 2010). Such forensic evidence needs to be presented in a way that a court of jurisprudence will accept it and adhere to the requirements set by legal authorities.

Forensic accounting, from the viewpoint of a fraud examiner, is the application of investigation and analytical abilities to resolve financial matters in a way that satisfies legal requirements mandated by courts (Hopwood et al, 2008). All things considered, forensic accounting investigations will require the expertise of an auditor, lawyer, and fraud examiner.

Skills and Education of the Forensic Investigator

Skills

I divide the forensic investigator's skill set into two groups in this section: basic abilities and augmented skills. This classification is comparable to that of Davis et al. (2010).

Core Skills:

The competencies deemed essential for becoming a forensic investigator are known as core competencies. For instance, Messmer (2004) found that intellectual aptitude, communication skills—both written and oral—a creative mindset, and business savvy. Ueltzen and Durkin (2009) emphasise that the forensic investigator needs to be knowledgeable of (i) practise management and professional obligations; (ii)

Top 10	Core Skill of the Forensic academic	Top Ranked Response	Core Skill of the Forensic Practitioner	Top Ranked Response	Core Skill of the Attorney	Top Ranked Response
1	Critical/strategic thinker	1 (62%)	Critical/strategic thinker	1 (50%)	Effective oral communicator	1 (61%)
2nd	Auditing skills	2 (53%)	Effective written communicator	2 (43%)	Simplify the information	2 (57%)
3rd	Investigative ability	3 (45%)	Effective oral communicator	3 (43%)	Critical/strategic thinker	3 (49%)
4th	Synthesize results of discovery and analysis	4 (43%)	Investigative ability	4 (41%)	Identify key issues	4 (38%)
5th	Think like the wrongdoer	5 (38%)	Investigative intuitiveness	5 (39%)	Auditing skills	5 (37%)
6th	Investigative intuitiveness	6 (36)	Synthesize results of discovery and analysis	6 (36%)	Investigative ability	5 (37%)
7th	Effective written communicator	7 (34%)	Organize an unstructured situation	7 (34%)	Synthesize results of discovery and analysis	5 (37%)
8th	Organize an unstructured situation	8 (32%)	Identify key issues	8 (32%)	Understand the goals of a case	8 (33%)
9th	Identify key issues	9 (30%)	Auditing skills	9 (31%)	Tell the story	9 (30%)
10th	Solve unstructured problems	9 (30%)	Solve unstructured problems	9 (31%)	See the big picture	9 (30%)
	Adapted from Davis et al (2010): p. 10.					

Enhanced skills:

Improved talents are those that have been acquired over years of work experience in the business or in university. Grippo and Ibex (2003) contend that forensic accountants' most crucial competencies originate from a background in management, internal controls, taxation, accounting, auditing, and human interactions, and correspondence. According to Ramaswamy (2005), abilities like: thorough understanding of financial statements, the capacity to evaluate analyse them and have a solid grasp of con games. Digabriele (2008) and Curtis (2008), among other studies, note that experts and professionals concur regarding the significance of a practical understanding of criminology and the judicial system as an improved ability.

According to Davis et al. (2010), fraud detection, interviewing techniques, financial statement analysis and interpretation, electronic discovery, general knowledge of rules of evidence and civil procedure and information, testifying, knowledge of pertinent professional standards, and so on are among the top enhanced skills for the forensic academic, practitioner, and attorney. The table illustrates how the relative significance of improved abilities varies depending on the needs of each industrial practise (academy and practise).

Enhanced skills						
Top 5	Skill of the Forensic Academic	Top Ranked Response	Skill of the Forensic Practitioner	Top Ranked Response	Core Skill of the Attorney	Top Ranked Response
1st	Fraud detection 1 (79%)	1 (79%)	Analyze and interpret financial statements and information	1 (79%)	Analyze and interpret financial statements and information	1 (91%)
2nd	Interviewing skills	2 (70%)	Interviewing skills	2 (63%)	Testifying	2 (74%)
3rd	Analyze and interpret financial statements and information	3 (64%)	Fraud detection	3 (56%)	Knowledge of relevant professional standards	3 (70%)
4th	Electronic discovery	4 (43%)	Testifying	4 (49%)	Audit evidence	4 (53%)
5th	General knowledge of rules of evidence and civil procedure	4 (43%)	General knowledge of rules of evidence and civil procedure	4 (39%)	Fraud detection	4 (53%)

Education

Previous research indicates that the practise of forensic accounting is becoming more and more important in academic settings (e.g., Rezaee and Burton, 1997; Peterson and Reider, 1999, 2001; Rezaee, 2002; Crumbley et al, 2003). As a subfield of accounting, forensic accounting research calls for a wide range of multidisciplinary expertise, especially in the areas of company operations, psychology, human behaviour, and working knowledge of the legal system.

Regarding the general scope of forensic accounting, there seems to be some agreement (see, for example, Enofe et al. 2013). There are several advantages for educational stakeholders when tertiary institutions give forensic accounting a wide focus. In particular, academic institutions, students, and employers of accounting graduates are the three main stakeholders in accounting education that Buckhoff and Schrader (2000) contend gain from include forensic accounting as a course of study in the accounting curriculum. In a survey on the importance of forensic accounting among tertiary institutions, Peterson and Reider (2001) report that accounting instructors in universities accept the importance of forensic accounting.

Additional research looks at how many tertiary institutions' accounting programmes include forensic-related courses. The question of whether forensic-related subjects were taught in universities was examined by Groomer and Heinz (1994). They discovered proof that internal auditing courses included instruction on fraud-related subjects. Few colleges provide courses in fraud or forensic accounting, according to Rezaee et al. (1996). According to research done in 2000 by Buckhoff and

Schrader, US colleges regarded forensic accounting as being of modest importance for inclusion in the accounting curriculum.

However, there are differing opinions in various research about the inclusion of forensic accounting courses in academic curriculum. Rezaee and Burtin (1997) discovered that whereas academics prefer to incorporate forensic accounting into already-existing accounting courses, forensic accountants prefer to have forensic accounting taught as a stand-alone course. There are some disputes between academics and practitioners regarding the current topics included in the forensic accounting curriculum, according to Rezaee et al. (1996). The topical content of forensic accounting in accounting curricula is still up for debate and presents a promising avenue for further investigation.

Implication

The value of each talent at a given moment or fraud event will depend on the type of fraud event and the required depth of inquiry, despite the seeming lack of consensus on the forensic investigator's skill set. The literature's identification of the wide spectrum of forensic investigator competencies has the effect of expanding the purview of forensic accounting instruction at higher education institutions. First of all, it raises the question of whether forensic accounting students ought to study a broad variety of subjects, including criminology, psychology, financial analysis, auditing, and law. Second, a comprehensive approach to forensic accounting education suggests that it is doubtful that academic institutions' annual or termly curricula will sufficiently include in-depth forensic education, either as an independent study or as an integrated curriculum.

Therefore, it is necessary to specify the fundamentals of forensic accounting that should be taught in academic and professional settings. Since it can be challenging to distinguish between core and non-core areas of forensic accounting, the argument that academic institutions should concentrate on the core auditing and financial reporting content of forensic accounting education while professional institutions should concentrate on the legal and investigative content of forensic education is extremely important. It also prompts other queries, such as what subjects ought to be covered in accounting curricula and which ones shouldn't. Future study in these areas will continue to be beneficial.

Cost-Benefit Analysis of Fraud Investigation

Regulators (investigators) incur costs associated with looking into every fraud case that is reported. Because of this, it is improbable that every fraud case that is reported will have full (and equal) priority during the investigation. Furthermore, substantial resources won't be allocated equitably to all fraud instances if every case is taken under investigation. This is due to several valid factors. In order to identify true fraud, a substantial amount of resources must first be invested in the examination of possible fraud instances. Investigators find this work rewarding if it results in the identification of genuine fraud. In this instance, the offenders (businesses) would be punished and fined, allowing authorities (investigators) to retrieve a substantial amount of committed resources (in monetary terms) within the inquiry.

Regulators' responses to fraud cases or incidents are impacted by this loss of resources allocated to investigation. Regulators are discouraged from allocating equal investigative priority to each reported fraud case due to the high expense of fraud investigation. However, scholars emphasise that every case of fraud that is reported needs to be treated carefully. This is unlikely to be the case in practise because it is simple to understand why authorities respond differently to some reported fraud cases, much as doctors do not view all illnesses as life-threatening and do not devote large resources to this category of illness. Consequently, another reason for the differences in opinions between policy makers and academics is the costs and benefits of conducting a fraud investigation.

Research and Policy Gap: why forensic accounting research does not inform policy

Research in forensic accounting ought to be crucial in guiding policy and practise (audit). The potential of forensic accounting research to influence policy will determine its future. For the following reasons, however, forensic academic research has not made much of an impact on supervisory guidelines or policy.

1) The majority of empirical research focuses on examining companies with a background of deception. A prospective researcher will often use a number of statistical tests to bolster his expectation that fraud exists in their analysis when they are aware that organisations have engaged in fraudulent activities. Regulators don't find this forensic research technique to be very helpful. Conversely, regulators are responsible for identifying ongoing fraudulent activity within businesses, whereas academic research focuses on previous fraud incidents. If forensic accounting study turns its attention from companies with a history of fraud to companies without a history of fraud, academic research will influence legislation.

2) Regulators recognise that statistical techniques used to identify past fraud events may not always have a significant explanatory power to identify future fraud cases, especially when investigating fraud cases necessitates the use of alternative statistical-detection techniques. This is because of recent advances in our understanding of human behaviour and financial engineering.

A Policy Note

Another taxonomy of fraud that regulators and practitioners could find appealing is required to guide policy. This classification is justified by the fact that, despite regulators' opposition to fraud, not all fraud instances actually call for harsh regulatory punishment or discipline.

This is due to the high expenses and other resources associated with looking into fraudulent misbehaviours. I suggest that each reported fraud case should have its investigative priority determined by a classification of fraud based on (i) the amount of misrepresented transactions; (ii) the materiality of the accounting number involved; (iii) the degree of deceptive intent; and (iv) the hierarchical status of the perpetrator - individual or firm; and (v) whether such practises are acceptable within the acceptable industry standards.

I therefore divide fraud into two categories: "soft fraud" and "hard fraud." Any fraudulent activity by a company that is seen as lawful under industry norms and practises (or regulatory guidelines) but is viewed as unlawful outside of the industry is known as "soft fraud." These fraudulent activities include, but are not restricted to, manipulating accrual expenses and income, as well as managing earnings. Conversely, hard fraud refers to any fraudulent activity carried out by a company that is regarded as illegal both inside and outside the sector. This type of fraudulent activity involves, among other things, making up suppliers, debtors, and other identities. There must be severe regulatory disciplinary measures for this kind of fraud.

Conclusion

The nature of fraud, forensic accounting, the fundamental and advanced capabilities of forensic investigators, as well as concerns with forensic education, have all been covered in this review. This evaluation included a few policy and practical problems. In conclusion, it's critical to remember that even though forensic accounting is becoming increasingly popular among academics, the amount of evidence left behind by fraudsters will determine how far forward forensic accounting study may go. This is due to the fact that those who commit fraud do leave evidence behind. Regulators will, however, be increasingly concerned in the upcoming years about fraudsters who leave no evidence at all. If the offenders possess in-depth knowledge of accounting rules, auditing procedures, and investigation abilities, this will be a challenge for regulators.

This information will assist the offenders in getting rid of any potential evidence of fraud. In the upcoming years, this will continue to be a policy and supervisory concern. Lastly, how much forensic accounting influences practise and policy will also determine how far the field of forensic accounting literature advances.

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